

A Study on Neelpawan Baruah's Paintings Exploring the Integration of Traditional Knowledge into Contemporary Art Design for Social Development

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The artists and artwork of the past have a tremendous influence on contemporary art through traditional art. For instance, the surrounding landscape and residential areas inspire artists' paintings and sculptures.

In the context of social justice and decolonization, integrative arts integrate technical and artistic abilities with a focus on artistic and creative approaches, transdisciplinary art studies, and participation in the creative industries.

Many contemporary artists' use of colour, shape, and composition shows the influence of traditional art styles. These artists continue to improve our world with their fresh and inventive creations, which they make possible by studying and learning from their masters.

The use of space has become essential to the work of contemporary artists. Contemporary artists are now considering public spaces when displaying and installing their artwork. Simple objects are transformed and given life by contemporary art.

Assam's popular artist Neelpawan Baruah, who was born in 1936, is one of the most renowned artists in Assam and North-East India and has significantly influenced the conversation about modern art throughout the region. Neelpawan Baruah, who received a formal degree in fine arts from Santiniketan in 1968, pioneered a new direction in the art world with his artistic experiments and organizational leadership when he founded the Assam Fine Arts and Crafts Society in 1971.

Among Neelpawan Baruah's many creative endeavors are:

1. Use of Neo-vaishnavite images and folk motifs into his complex, textured paper-Mache work
2. Charminar cigarette packs have been utilized by Neelpawan Baruah as a creative and teaching tool.
3. Neelpawan Baruah's artistic exploration has resulted in drab card board match boxes.
4. The use of unconventional media to depict his subjects is highly valuable for contemporary art.

This present paper examines how traditional knowledge can be integrated with contemporary art design for social development through the paintings of Neelpawan Baruah.